

THE USE OF INTEGRATION WITH OTHER SUBJECTS TO TEACH ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Ilmiy rahbar: **Axmedov Hasan Uzairovich**
Sharipova Nodira Shavkat qizi

Toshkent viloyati , Chirchiq davlat pedagogika universiteti
Turizm fakulteti Xorijiy til va adabiyoti- ingliz tili, 21/4 guruh talabasi

Abstract: *The conditions created and the rapid changes and developments taking place in the environment, but in this article as we work in part-time pedagogical work from foreign languages in primary school – we would like to share my thoughts on how to use English language teaching in conjunction with other subjects, i.e., the integration of disciplines, and how to easily explain English words to primary school students. The article highlights teaching English in several integrated ways.*

Keywords: *integration, teaching, EFL, English, methodology, pedagogy, learners.*

From time immemorial, the study of language and through it the discovery of a new world and culture for itself has been one of the most pressing issues, and it has not lost its degree even today. Therefore, a number of measures are being taken in our country to increase language learning literacy. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-1975 of December 10, 2012 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Learning Foreign Languages", May 8, 2013 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Learning Foreign Languages" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. VM-124 "On Approval of the State Standard of Education", December 31, 2013 "On Approval of the Regulation on the Procedure for Determining the Level of Knowledge of a Foreign Language and Issuing a Qualification Certificate" about Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. VM-352 of October 10, 2013 "On the procedure for conducting tests to determine the monthly increase in the basic salary of teachers of foreign languages under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Order of the Director of the State Testing Center DTM 01-339 "On approval" and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August

11, 2017 "On measures to further improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions" Resolution VM-610 is one of them.

We aren't indifferent to the above-mentioned decisions and orders, the conditions created and the rapid changes and developments taking place in the environment, but in this article as we work in part-time pedagogical work from foreign languages in primary school – we would like to share my thoughts on how to use English language teaching in conjunction with other subjects, i.e., the integration of disciplines, and how to easily explain English words to primary school students. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Our most important task is to create an innovative environment in the worldview of our people. Without innovation, there can be no competition, no development in any field. If we do not promote the changes in this area to our people, if we do not develop skills in people, we will not be able to keep pace with the intensity of today's times, the unprecedented achievements of science and technology."

The process of education and upbringing as a complex pedagogical process requires the education and upbringing of students during each lesson hour. Whatever the subject, the subject must have a specific purpose, content, and essence in order for students to be formed as individuals, as full members of society. In this regard, emphasizing the attention paid to the teaching of foreign languages in the education system today, as well as the interest of students in learning foreign languages, we can say that in the teaching of foreign languages, education and adherence to the unity of upbringing is bound to have a positive effect on the formation of a harmoniously developed generation. For a child who has just entered school, learning a new language can be a little daunting. Therefore, we can solve this problem by using the integrated method in language teaching. However, in many sources, grammar is described as the rules that make up the language structure. Children have a hard time mastering the rules and get bored as a result. Interestingly, language grammar seems to be a difficult field to learn, even for adults. In my opinion, this is not the case. It is well known that it is necessary to simply simplify the ways of presenting grammar and make it really interesting. In order to teach young children, the grammar of a foreign language, language teachers need to make the material a little easier, simpler, and increase children's interest. Because of the ability of cognitive analysis in young children is not yet formed. For students of this age, the use of the principle of demonstration in the teaching of a subject,

especially a foreign language, gives good results. Children do not need to have a perfect knowledge of grammar to be able to communicate simply in English. It is natural that grammar rules seem boring to children. It has been proven in psychology that young children are full of courage. This means that the material presented to children should be primarily interesting and understandable and enjoyable for children.

1. *Art.* If we start learning a new subject together with the subjects that the student likes, we will succeed. Take the ART as an example. Most children go to school at the age of 6 or 7. At this age, in addition to learning new knowledge, there will be a great interest in drawing and painting. We can teach students fruits and vegetables by connecting English with pictures. We ask the pupil to draw a picture of the fruit, and colour it. Once the pupil has completed, we will instill in the child's mind how to pronounce the name of this fruit in English and its colors. For example, if there is a picture of an apple: It is an apple. It is red and green. It is a banana. It is yellow. It is an orange. It is orange. The same with vegetables, It is an onion. It is white. Or It is a cabbage. It is green. Next, "What is it?", "What color is it?" It is enough to mention this picture as an answer to our questions.

2. *Mathematics.* To teach children numbers, of course, mathematics helps us. Gradually the pupil begins to read and learns to add and subtract one-digit numbers in a math lesson. After learning the name of numbers in English first, we use addition and subtraction in mathematics, a favourite subject of children in mathematics. For example, by asking how many objects and objects are in the room, we can also return the subject of numbers, and also $1 + 3 = 4$ (one plus three it is four), $2 + 4 = 6$ (two plus four it is six), 9 Examples such as $-7 = 2$ (nine minus seven it is two), $8-5 = 3$ (eight minus five it is three), further increase children's interest in English.

3. *Music.* Kids love to listen to music and dance. Putting interesting and cheerful music in English in each lesson and teaching them dance moves in accordance with these musical words will give the child a broader understanding of the material being studied. If we repeat these songs in each lesson, children will instinctively learn to pronounce these words correctly in their minds (on the subject of fruits and vegetables) and to show them (on the subject of body parts). It should be noted that it is difficult for young children to sit in one place for 45 minutes. Through this music and action games, the child will not get bored.

4. *Alphabet, reading.* As students begin to recognize the gaps, reading new things in them will encourage them to read from their teacher and parents, and will also encourage them to read more and more. In

doing so, we can show that they are different from their native language by teaching the letters of the English language. In English the letters are radically different in that they are read and written differently. This is why elementary grades will have difficulty mastering these. If we only teach them the English alphabet, we will teach them the difference in reading and writing slowly as they learn.

In conclusion, language learning can be a difficult issue when the learner is not interested in it, but we can solve it using a variety of methodologies and tools, and the integration method is also helpful in this regard. After all, it is in the hands of teachers to teach children to open up new worlds, to engage them and increase their love for science.

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